

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of some Aryl Methyl Sulphides by Thallium(III) in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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Manuscript received 5 July 1988, revised 18 October 1988, accepted 14 December 1988

ALTHOUGH kinetics of oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides have been studied extensively using several oxidising agents¹, kinetic studies using the metal ion species as oxidants are rather limited. Satyanarayana *et al.*² reported the oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides by vanadium(v) and proposed a polar mechanism while the oxidation by chromium(vi) is characterised by a single-electron transfer process³. The strikingly different mechanisms proposed for the oxidation by two metal ion species prompted us to take up the present work using thallium(III) as the oxidising agent, though the same has been used for the oxidation of a wide variety of organic substrates^{4,5}. The present communication reports our results on the kinetic study on the oxidation of some aryl methyl sulphides by thallium(III).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Acetic acid was purified over chromium trioxide. Thallium(III) acetate (TA) was prepared by dissolving thallic oxide (B.D.H.) in aqueous acetic acid. The sulphides were prepared by the known procedures. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted thallium(III) iodometrically⁶. The reactions were conducted under second order conditions using sulphide excess over TA.

By carrying out different sets of experiments with varying ratios of sulphide to TA (TA > sulphide), it was concluded that one mole of any sulphide consumed one mole of TA yielding the corresponding sulphoxide. The product analysis carried out for sulphides (nmr, tlc) revealed that the product is only sulphoxide and in no case the higher oxidation product sulphone was detected. The stoichiometric equation may be written as

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of a series of aryl methyl sulphides by TA have been carried out in aqueous acetic acid at constant acidity and ionic strength. The reaction is practically negligible in the absence of added mineral acids and is conveniently carried out by maintaining required concentration of sulphuric

acid. The second order rate constants determined were highly reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ error. The oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide (MPS) has been studied in greater detail.

The second order rate constants for the oxidation of MPS by TA are given in Table 1. Variation of either [MPS] or [TA] has no appreciable effect on the rate constants indicating that the reaction follows a second order—first order each in MPS and TA. The rate of oxidation of MPS by TA is not affected by change in the ionic strength of the medium (ionic strength is changed by adding required amounts of sodium sulphate at constant [H⁺]) indicating that the reaction is between an ion and a dipole molecule.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [MPS] AND [TA] ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF MPS BY TA

Solvent = 75% aq. acetic acid, [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 40°

[MPS] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[TA] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k ₂ × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.50	7.57	2.12
2.18	7.57	2.12
2.65	7.57	2.11
3.16	7.57	2.14
4.88	7.08	2.12
7.82	7.08	2.16
2.89	1.26	2.18
2.39	2.48	2.11
2.16	3.68	2.10
2.16	5.04	2.19
2.39	8.84	2.11
2.39	9.54	2.12

As mentioned earlier the oxidation of MPS by TA is negligible in the absence of added mineral acid and increases with the increase in [H⁺] at constant ionic strength (Table 2). Therefore, on

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

[MPS] ≈ 2.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [TA] ≈ 7.67 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Solvent = 75% aq. acetic acid, Temp. = 40°

[H ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k ₂ × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.7	0.59
0.8	0.70
0.9	1.10
1.0	2.12
1.10	2.25
1.20	3.23
1.30	5.04

the basis of the absence of salt effect, it was concluded that H⁺ ions only are responsible for the increase in the rate. The order with respect to H⁺ was found to be slightly greater than unity from the slope of the plot log [H⁺] vs log k. On this basis, Tl(OAc)₂⁺ may be considered to be the active species,

In order to further confirm that $Tl(OAc)_2^+$ is participating in the rate-determining step, the reaction between MPS and TA was carried out in solvent media containing different compositions of acetic acid-water mixtures. The reaction is strongly dielectric-dependent and was found to increase with the increase in percentage of acetic acid, i.e. with decrease in the dielectric constant (Table 3). For

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

$[MPS] \approx 2.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[TA] \approx 7.61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 40°

Solvent composition (%) HOAc-H ₂ O	k_2 $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
80-20	4.47
75-25	3.12
70-30	1.22
65-35	0.93

the limiting case of a head on collision of an ion with dipole molecule, Emis⁶ gave an equation, according to which a decrease in dielectric constant should increase the rate for the reaction of a positive ion and dipole molecule. The decrease in rate with increase in water content in the solvent medium may also be explained by considering the increased solvation of the sulphide group and its consequent decreased nucleophilicity. A similar observation was made by Overberger and Cummins⁷ in the oxidation of sulphides to sulfoxides.

Although $Tl(OAc)_3$ has been suggested to be the active species in redox reactions, the rate-dependence on dielectric constant of the medium suggests a positive thallic ion species as an active oxidant in the present study. Henry⁸ also reported $Tl(OAc)_2^+$ to be the most active electrophilic species in aqueous acetic acid.

Substituents effect: The second order rate constants for the oxidation of some *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulphides at 40, 45 and 50° are presented in Table 4 along with the relevant

TABLE 4—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS, ENTHALPIES AND ENTROPIES OF ACTIVATION FOR THE OXIDATION OF *meta*- AND *para*-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL METHYL SULPHIDES BY TIII

Solvent = 65% aq. acetic acid, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Substituent	$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	40°	45°	50°		
None	0.92	1.86	1.98	61.8	143.3
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	245.30	—	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	12.72	20.76	30.57	70.95	92.8
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.15	0.39	1.08	163.6	165.8
<i>p</i> -Br	0.52	0.54	1.63	93.4	49.3
<i>p</i> -I	0.14	0.25	0.39	80.72	98.8
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.013	0.023	0.092	74.73	137.9
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	0.64	0.90	1.18	49.00	187.9
<i>m</i> -OH ₂	2.37	3.06	5.64	69.99	110.6
<i>m</i> -Cl	0.031	0.033	0.091	88.45	88.5
<i>m</i> -Br	0.27	0.29	0.45	40.5	223.0
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.031	0.031	0.044	27.56	232.2

thermodynamic parameters. It is clear that the electron-donating substituents in benzene ring accelerate the rate while the electron-withdrawing ones retard. A plot of $\log k$ vs σ constants gave a fair correlation with negative value of the reaction constant ($\rho = -3.36$, $r = -0.90$) at 313 K. The negative ρ indicates the development of a positive charge in the reaction centre in the transition state. However, the correlation was well improved when σ^+ values were used for *para*-substituents ($\rho^+ = -2.7$, $r = -0.96$). The negative ρ^+ value indicates that the transition state is stabilised by electron-releasing *para*-substituents. The high negative reaction constant clearly points to an ionic mechanism.

The absence of polymer formation when the reaction was conducted in the presence of acrylonitrile monomer, indicates the non-involvement of intermediate free radicals where the reaction constant is less than or nearly unity⁹.

The isokinetic relationship was verified using Exner¹⁰ analysis. A plot of $\log k_{40}$ vs $\log k_{50}$ gave an excellent linear correlation ($r = 0.98$) indicating that all the sulphides undergo oxidation through the same mechanism.

The foregoing experimental observations reveal that the probable mechanism (Scheme 1) involves

Scheme 1 Mechanism for the oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides by TA.

the rate-determining formation of a thallation adduct by the nucleophilic participation of sulphur of sulphide. The sulphonium cation hydrolyses in a fast step giving the corresponding sulphoxide. Such nucleophilic participation by sulphur of sulphide was also observed in other oxidation reactions of sulphides¹⁰ and sulphoxides¹¹. The rate law may be given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} &= k[MPS][Tl(OAc)_2^+] \\
 &= kK[ArSCH_3][Tl(OAc)_2][H^+]
 \end{aligned}$$

